

ESTIMATION OF FORMATES BY OXIDATION WITH MERCURIC CHLORIDE

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A specific method, applicable in presence of salts of other organic acids, is described for the volumetric and gravimetric estimation of formate ion. The precision of the volumetric method is 0.5% or more. An isobrometric procedure, suitable for micro estimation of quantities as low as 1 mg. of formic acid, has also been evolved.

Fuchs (*Z. anal. Chem.*, 1929, 78, 125) determined neutral alkali formates by titration of the hydrochloric acid liberated during its oxidation with mercuric chloride.

Instead of using an indicator, Fuchs titrated with alkali to the appearance of a yellow precipitate of mercuric oxide. Oldeman (*Pharm. Weekblad*, 1931, 68, 379) recommended titration to phenolphthalein end-point after adding sodium chloride to tie up the excess of mercuric chloride. The latter procedure was found to afford an error of 3-4%. The present communication describes a modification of the same, offering more precise results.

EXPERIMENTAL

Formic acid and sodium hydroxide used were of A. R. quality. Potassium iodide, sodium iodate, sodium acetate and mercuric chloride were of Merk's chemically pure variety. Standard solutions of sodium formate were prepared by neutralising formic acid solutions with CO₂-free NaOH solution in presence of phenolphthalein. As alcohol was found to interfere, dry crystals of the indicator were used. The CO₂-free alkali was prepared by Sørensen's strong alkali procedure (*Biochem. Z.*, 1909, 21, 168) and stored in an aspirator fitted with sodalime tube. The standard solutions for micro-estimations were prepared by diluting the N/10 solutions 10 to 50 times with conductivity water.

Volumetric Estimation.—The neutral formate solution (20-25 c.c.) containing not more than 50 mg. of formic acid was pipetted into a 150 c.c. pyrex conical flask and treated with 10 c.c. of 15% sodium acetate (formate-free) solution. The air in the flask was as far as possible displaced by steam which was passed into it without actually bubbling through the solution. A saturated mercuric chloride solution (20 c.c., 7.1%) was quickly added and the flask closed with a rubber cork which was pressed in with a little force. Heating was carried out in an electrically heated water-bath by placing the flask in boiling water so as to immerse only its lower part containing the solution. Further, it was weighted by a band of lead which encircled its lower portion. As the flask developed a slight pressure, the bath was placed in a corner of a room, protected by flame guards, and left undisturbed except for the addition of water from time to time. The steaming was found to reduce

the pressure considerably and prevented blowing off of the cork. After half an hour's heating the bath was switched off and allowed to cool. The flask was finally cooled under the tap, its stopper removed and the contents boiled for half a minute by placing it on an electrical hot plate (pre-heated). The total period of heating on the hot plate was limited to 2 or 3 minutes during which time all the CO_2 was found to escape. The flask was again stoppered and allowed to cool when its contents were filtered through a sintered crucible (G4), using about 40 c.c. of water for washing. The filtrate which was received in a 250 c.c. filter flask was treated with an excess of solid potassium iodide (4 g.) till the red precipitate first formed completely dissolved, and then it was titrated with 0.1N-NaOH solution to phenolphthalein end-point. The results of evaluation of six different solutions, carried out in duplicates, as recorded in Table I, revealed that the experimental values compared favourably with the actual values and the error which was always on the lower side did not exceed 0.5% (1 c.c. of 0.1N alkali corresponds to 4.6 mg. of formic acid).

TABLE I

Expt. No.	F o r m i c a c i d (mg.) by				
	V o l u m e t r i c.			G r a v i m e t r i c.	
	Calc.	Found.	Error.	Found.	Error.
1.	50.5 mg.	50.3 mg.	-0.4%	50.1 mg.	-0.8%
2.	46.0	45.8	-0.5	46.1	+0.2
3.	42.2	42.1	-0.3	41.9	-0.7
4.	40.3	40.3	Nil	40.6	+0.8
5.	37.4	37.2	-0.5	36.9	-1.3
6.	36.1	36.0	-0.3	36.2	+0.3

Gravimetric Estimation.—The reaction was carried out in a manner similar to that described above. The white precipitate of mercurous chloride obtained was filtered through a weighed sintered crucible (G4) and repeatedly washed with about 100 c.c. of water and finally with 25 c.c. of acetone. The crucible was allowed to dry at room temperature (22°) by leaving it overnight, slightly inclined, on a clean table and then weighed. From the weight of mercurous chloride, the formic acid content was calculated. One gram of the chloride is equivalent to 97.45 mg. of formic acid. The results of gravimetric and volumetric estimations of the same aliquots are recorded in Table I.

Micro-estimation.—Neutral formate solution (1-10 c.c.) containing 1-5 mg. of formic acid was pipetted into a 150 c.c. pyrex conical flask. After displacing the air inside the flask by steam, a saturated mercuric chloride solution (20 c.c.) was quickly added and then it was closed with a good compressed bark cork. The flask was heated in boiling water in the manner already described. The gas pressure developed inside it was not much as only about 2 c.c. of CO_2 was produced during the reaction, which took considerable time (2-3 hrs.) as its velocity diminished with increase in H^+ -ion concentration. After the reaction was over, the solution was cooled and filtered through a sintered crucible by applying a mild suction. Minimum quantity of

conductivity water was used for washing and transferring the filtrate to a 250 c.c. conical flask. The filtrate was treated with an excess of solid potassium iodide (4.5 g.) and sodium iodate (0.5 g.) and then left in the dark for 5 minutes for complete oxidation of the H^+ ions ($IO_3^- + 5I^- + 6H^+ \rightarrow 3I_2 + 3H_2O$). The solutions being very dilute, this process of oxidation was found to take a little time. Darkness was sought to prevent oxidation of potassium iodide; a closed cupboard was found suitable for the purpose. The iodine liberated was finally titrated with 0.01 *N* hypo solution taken in a 10 c.c. micro-burette, using 2 c.c. of 1% starch solution as indicator (1 c.c. of 0.01 *N* hypo solution $\equiv$ 0.46 mg. of formic acid). The results of assay of six different solutions are recorded in Table II. The precision is about 1%, the error a'ways occurring on the lower side.

TABLE II

Expt. No.	I_2 liberated. (0.01 <i>N</i>)	Formic acid.		% Error.
		Present.	Found.	
1.	2.20 c.c.	1.012 mg.	1.012 mg.	Nil
2.	4.35	2.024	2.001	-1.1
3.	5.46	2.530	2.512	-0.7
4.	6.55	3.036	3.013	-0.8
5.	8.74	4.048	4.020	-0.7
6.	10.90	5.060	5.014	-0.9

CONCLUSION

The macro (volumetric) method has certain advantages as well as disadvantages. The procedure has the usefulness of being applicable in presence of salts of other acids, weak as well as strong. But its greatest drawback lies in the fact that it finally gives rise to a solution containing a mixture of carbon dioxide and acetic acid, out of which the former has to be completely driven off. If the heating is carried out longer than necessary, some acetic acid is also lost, while insufficient heating affords higher values due to the retention of some carbon dioxide. The micro procedure appears to be more elegant as it does away with this difficulty and also possesses a sharp end-point. But it has the disadvantage of being inapplicable in presence of salts of other weak acids which make the process of oxidation of the H^+ ions by IO_3^- and I^- ions incredibly slow and impracticable. Where high precision is not required, the gravimetric procedure will be found more suitable as it has none of the disadvantages mentioned above.

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